

Efficient T2* spin-level simulation

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION: Simulation plays an important role in MRI development, research, and education [1], especially at the spin level since this type of simulation captures more faithfully the physical phenomena. Some tissue parameters are well modeled and easy to simulate (i.e., the density and T2 or T1), but simulating T2* is challenging because it depends on local micro variations of the magnetic field. To accurately represent T2* decay many isochromats per location are required, increasing the computational load. We propose a mechanism for optimally choosing the number, frequency, and location of the isochromats for obtaining a signal representing the T2* decay.

METHODS: When the frequencies of isochromats for a given location follow a Lorentzian distribution (LD), the signal has an exponential decay with T2*. We propose optimal sampling of the LD to reduce required number of isochromats and to jointly consider sampling in space (typical in spin-level simulations) with sampling in frequency (needed for T2* decay). We choose the frequency sampling of the LD [2] of a reduced number of spins by choosing M frequencies ω that best approximate the ideal FID signal, minimizing the Mean Square Error (MSE) between both signals. We optimized only once for a T2* value, and the M frequencies are scaled to find them for other values.

A typical simulation will use several spins spatially located more densely than the expected resolution of the reconstruction. A direct solution for adding T2* decay would require locating M isochromats (with the frequencies found in the previous section) at each spin location. Here we experiment with the idea of using a different random subset of $L \leq M$ isochromats at each location. The rationale is that values associated to the pixels will be obtained by some averaging, including information from many different frequencies. We assume that the number of spins is J times larger than the number of pixels in each dimension. To simulate a generic sequence, for each time instant we convolved the signal with a sinc function adapted to the pixel size. This filtered signal is then sampled at the pixel locations, and ρ and T2* are estimated: ρ as the value of the signal for $t=0$, and T2* by fitting an exponential decay to the signal.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION: We did 2D simulations, employing ρ and T2* phantoms. Fig. 1a shows the optimal 11 frequencies (top), uniformly sampling the cumulative distribution function (Deterministic) with 21 frequencies (middle) and random Lorentzian with 100 frequencies (bottom). All configurations give a similar MSE of 0.0093 between ideal and simulated FID, as shown in Fig 1b. Fig. 1c shows a 2D phantom, and Fig 1d, the simulation reconstruction, showing a good match for a total of 176 (4x4x11) isochromats per pixel. We also show (Fig. 1e,f) the signal from the simulation (blue dots), the exponential fit (red line) and the theoretical decay (green line) for red and blue points in Fig. 1c.

Figure 1: (a) Isochromat frequencies, (b) Correspondent signal obtained (blue) and ideal FID signal (orange) for global optimization with M=11 (upper row), deterministic frequencies with M=21 (middle) and random frequencies with M=100 (bottom). (c) ρ and T2* phantom with two singular points marked in red and blue; (d) Simulation (M=L=11, J=4); (e | f) Signal (blue line), fitting (red), and FID signal (black) for red | blue point in (a).

References

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